

(1) Overview

Title

SODAsim (Step-by-step Operating Discrete Automaton SIMulator): A programmable discrete and cellular automaton simulator

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Abstract

SODAsim is used for modeling autonomous discrete or cellular automata using a standalone Python GUI hosted on GitHub. The step-by-step format guides the user through the creation of an array of regularly connected shapes and design of a state diagram. Unlike traditional cellular automata, SODAsim may optionally include named numerical values, called properties, facilitating simulation of processes such as contagious illness, pathfinding, and tissue morphogenesis. Single line statements supplied by the user define the operation of the system and employ typical programming functions, as well as custom SODAsim functions and syntax that allow a great degree of complexity. The simulation viewer at the end displays computed time steps in sequence and has multiple viewing options to visually capture phenomena of interest. Simulation parameters and steps may be saved and loaded as needed.

Keywords

discrete/cellular automata simulator, programmable, standalone, multipurpose

Introduction

A classical automaton consists of a finite number of inputs and a single output, each of which may be “on” or “off”. The internal logic of the automaton specifies whether the output will be “on” as a function of the set of inputs that are “on”, and this output will be produced after a discrete time interval, hence “discrete automaton” (1). Using these concepts to model biological systems in abstract terms was first undertaken by John von Neumann in his 1966 introduction of cellular automata, in which he explored the requirements for self-replicating machines (2).

To build a cellular automaton, several of these automata may be formed into a network by feeding the output of one automaton into other automaton(s) as an input. The collection of inputs feeding into an automaton determines the “state” of the automaton, which in turn selects the logic used to compute the output. All units of the complex follow the same clock and the same rules, and the output of each unit at a particular step depends only upon the previous step. Such arrangements are capable of unintuitively complex output patterns that derive autonomously from only an initial set of inputs (3). John Conway furthered this research in creating his “Game of Life” in 1970, one of the most recognizable and enduringly popular examples of a cellular automaton (4).

Many others formalized the mathematical study of cellular automata by introducing taxonomic categories for the behavior of models, rigorously proving new theorems, and creating models fulfilling the earlier work of Alan Turing on universal computers (5). Application of cellular automata as a modeling tool has also gained momentum in biology (6) and physics (7), and in unexpected disciplines, such as in models of vehicular traffic flow and population growth (8). The needs of these disparate subjects have led to the creation of many simulators in the form of websites and downloadable software. Many tools exist solely for playing Conway’s Game of Life and related rules, with some of these tools allowing the state transition conditions to be adjusted based on the number of neighbors in the “alive” and “dead” states (9). CellLab allows the user greater flexibility to alter the rules of the state diagram by creating a JavaScript file with custom states and state transition conditions. The simulation operates on a square grid with multiple options of neighborhood (10). The software Morpheus is designed for cell and tissue simulations and allows great flexibility within this domain with many preset options supporting modeling biological processes (11).

Herein is introduced SODAsim, a multipurpose, programmable software for modeling discrete and cellular automata within any discipline. The small inventory of keywords and functions allows state transition conditions and values of properties to be expressed easily with single-line expressions, rather than files of code requiring knowledge of programming. Custom functions include noise generation and sampling, which are useful for simulating non-deterministic processes. The addition of properties extends SODAsim beyond the traditional framework for cellular automata, allowing modeling of more complex situations that cannot be represented fully by states in a state diagram, like infectious disease spread and chemical gradients.

These features also make SODAsim well-suited for modeling spatially structured biological systems in which local interactions produce emergent system-level behavior. For example, host-associated microbial communities often depend upon spatial organization, barrier integrity, diffusion gradients, and dynamic interactions among multiple cell or microbial types. By combining programmable state transitions with continuously variable properties, SODAsim enables simulation of how local interactions among neighboring units may collectively alter tissue permeability, microbial connectivity, or host exposure over time.

Unlike many existing cellular automata platforms that focus primarily on predefined rule sets or highly specialized domains, SODAsim integrates spatial geometry, neighborhood logic, programmable state transitions, and continuously variable scalar properties within a unified graphical workflow. This combination enables users to construct complex, spatially explicit simulations without extensive programming, while preserving flexibility to model emergent behaviors across diverse systems. By allowing local interactions and property dynamics to reshape system-level organization over time, SODAsim is particularly well suited for exploratory and hypothesis-generating applications in which spatial structure and interaction rules co-evolve.

Implementation and architecture

The interface for SODAsim is organized as a set of pages in which the user enters parameters step-by-step to define a simulation, proceeding to the next page when the requirements for the current page have been satisfied. Pages 1-7 of SODAsim contain tools for inputting a set of parameters, and page 8 for generating and viewing a simulation. The user is guided in numerical order through the pages shown in the diagram below, from page 0 to page 8.

Figure 1: Pages of SODAsim

Arrows connect each parameter to dependent parameter(s). Changing a parameter, by clicking the “Add” or “Delete” buttons or using the ↑ and ↓ arrow buttons, causes all dependent parameters to be reset to empty. For example, changing the BOUNDARIES parameter will reset the shapes array and require PROPAGATION to be performed again, which will reset the data from INITIAL STATES, which will reset the data from SIMULATION, including a currently active simulation.

Parameters may be saved to a file on the INITIAL STATES page after selecting an initial state for all shapes, and this file may be loaded on the INTRO page to automatically populate parameters. Once parameters have been loaded or entered, the user can proceed to the SIMULATION page and begin generating simulations based on these parameters. Simulation steps may be saved and loaded on this page. An Excel spreadsheet containing all simulation data at each time step may be generated and saved as well. The sections below expand on each page of SODAsim.

0. INTRO

This page contains a scrolling canvas containing instructions, a list of keywords and functions, and explained examples for using SODAsim. The selector to the right of the instructions has options:

- **New simulation:** the user will be prompted over the following pages to enter parameters for a new, custom simulation

- **Example simulation:** a popup window will prompt the user to select from a dropdown menu of example simulations, and the parameters of the selected choice will automatically populate pages 1-7; parameters may be viewed, but must not be altered to avoid possible deletion of dependent parameters
- **Saved simulation:** a popup window will prompt the user to enter the filename of the file containing parameters (which must have been previously saved on the INITIAL STATES page), and the parameters of the selected choice will automatically populate pages 1-7; parameters may be viewed, but must not be altered to avoid possible deletion of dependent parameters

One of the above options must be selected and fulfilled.

1. PRESET

This page allows the user to select the shape to be used for simulations. The “shape” is a discrete operational unit that is regularly spaced and related to neighboring shapes, and could represent a person, biological cell, or other discrete unit. The shape appears on the canvas as a polygon containing the origin. Some shapes appear multiple times in the drop-down list because there are multiple options for the number of neighbors, which is discussed further down in this explanation. The last option, “custom”, allows the user to define a custom shape on the SHAPE page.

2. SHAPE

If a shape and neighbor combination was selected on the PRESET page, this page displays the selected shape. If “custom” was selected, then the user must define a polygon by entering vertices as (x, y) coordinates and adding to the list by clicking the “Add” button. The edges of the polygon are formed by connecting adjacent vertices in the list, so deleting vertices or using the ↑ and ↓ arrow buttons to change the order of the vertices will change the edges of the polygon. This polygon must contain the origin, which may be within the enclosed area or along an edge or vertex. As the initial shape in the array of shapes, this shape will be referred to as shape 0.

A polygon must include:

- at least three vertices
- no duplicated vertices
- segments that are not collinear
- edges that intersect only at the vertices
- nonzero area

Vertices of a shape selected on the PRESET page may be added, deleted, or reordered, but doing so will reset dependent parameters.

3. NEIGHBORS

If a shape and neighbor combination was selected on the PRESET page, this page displays the selected shape with neighbors. If “custom” was selected on the PRESET page, then the user may define a set of neighboring shapes using the x, y, and \ominus entry

fields. For each neighbor of shape 0, the x and y values represent the horizontal and vertical displacement of the neighbor from shape 0, and the Θ value represents the counterclockwise rotation (measured in degrees) of the neighbor relative to shape 0. The set of neighbors describes how shapes are connected to one another in that each shape within the array connects to its neighbors in the same way when adjusted for rotation. Neighbors may have $(x, y) = (0, 0)$ if the corresponding Θ value is not 0 or a multiple of 360. Clicking the “Add” button appends the new neighbor shape to the list of neighbors, which are labeled N_1, N_2, \dots, N_n etc. on the diagram. Neighbors do not need to be physically adjacent. Adding neighbors is not required, but the simulation will utilize only one shape if neighbors are not added.

Figure 2: Preset shape and neighbor combinations

In each diagram below, shape 0 is outlined in red and each neighbor is shaded in green. These options may be selected on the PRESET page.

4. BOUNDARIES

Boundaries define the spatial extent of the array of shapes. A boundary is added by entering points as (x, y) coordinates such that line segments connect adjacent points, in the same manner as on the SHAPE page. Once complete, this list of points may be added as either a normal boundary or as an inverse boundary.

3D simulations may be constructed as a set of 2D layers by using multiple boundaries, as illustrated in the 3D diffusion example.

Table 1: Boundaries and inverse boundaries

	boundary	inverse boundary
requirement	1+ (at least one boundary must enclose shape 0)	0 (optional)
description	Must be a polygon	May be a single point, line segment, or polygon
function	All shapes must be contained by at least one boundary and may overlap at edges	Shapes may not share contain or share area with an inverse boundary, but may overlap at edges

PROPAGATION

Data from SHAPE, NEIGHBORS, and BOUNDARIES pages are used to create an array of shapes on this page. For shape 0, the anchor is always (0, 0) and the rotation is always 0° , so (0, 0, 0) becomes the first item of the array of shapes. To form neighbor shape n , the vertices of shape 0 are rotated about the origin by Θ_n , then translated by (x_n, y_n) . If this neighbor is fully within at least one boundary and does not overlap any inverse boundaries, then the tuple (x_n, y_n, Θ_n) will be appended to the array of shapes. If no neighbors of shape 0 are included in the array, the array will have only one shape. Otherwise, the propagation process will advance to the next shape in the list, compute each neighbor of that shape, and append that shape to the array if it meets the boundary conditions. Propagation continues until the end of the array is reached and no further shapes can be added.

Shape anchors are rounded to 10 decimal places to prevent overlap due to floating point errors. Shapes are filled in different colors to make overlaps easily visible. Press The “Pause” button may be pressed to pause propagation so that the user can adjust data on previous pages to prevent undesired overlap.

To minimize the size of parameters files, shapes data is not saved; the user must click the “Propagate” button to generate an array of shapes for all simulations. Dependent parameters will be reset only if the number of shapes in the array changes.

STATES

On this page, the user defines a state diagram governing behavior of shapes, including transitions between states and values of properties. The scrolling image in the INTRO section contains several examples with explanations to further clarify the creation of state diagrams and expressions.

A **state** is a category in which a shape exists. Each shape must be in one and only one state during each time step, so at least one state must be added to the simulation. The state of a shape determines how the shape interacts with other shapes and may influence the values of properties of that shape. To add a state to the canvas, double-click on the canvas and supply a name and color on the menu appearing on the right. States can be dragged and dropped to a new location on the canvas as needed. The

selected color is how shapes in the state will appear on the SIMULATION page while state data is being viewed. To add a transition from one state to another, click the “Add transition” button, select the initial and final states, and supply an expression as the transition condition.

A **property** is a numerical, scalar attribute of shapes. Adding properties is optional, and as many may be added as desired. Each shape must have a scalar value for each property during each time step. To add a property, click the “Add property” button and supply a name for the property; all other property value expressions below the name may be entered later by clicking on the property name. The required property value expressions for property P for state S are as follows:

- initial value of property P in state S (written P_0): the value of property P for shapes in state S at time step 0 (may reference initial states, but must not reference property values)
- change in value of property P in state S during each time step (written ΔP): the *change* of property P for shapes in state S during a time step (enter 0 if no change in value is to occur)
- value of property P in state S after transition $R \rightarrow S$ (written $P_{R \rightarrow S}$): the value of property P for shapes upon transitioning from state R to state S (use the expression “val(self, P)” for the value to remain the same)

All expressions for time step T are computed based on the states and property values of shapes in time step T-1. Changes in values of property P are computed first, then transition conditions are evaluated based on these changed values and required transitions are executed, and a new value of property P is assigned if a transition has occurred based on changed property values and newly assigned states.

Transition conditions and property values (discussed below) are **expressions**, which are single lines of code, either supplied by the user or loaded as part of an example or saved simulation, that are evaluated to produce a numerical, scalar value. Expressions may themselves be scalar values (ex. 0, 5, -1), may include state names and property names, and may include the keywords and/or functions listed in Table 2 below.

Table 2: A complete list of SODAsim keywords and functions

SODAsim keywords	
index	refers to the index of the reference shape (numbering begins with shape 0)
timestep	refers to the current time step (simulation begins at time step 0)
numshapes	refers to the total number of shapes
True	1
False	0

Mathematical functions	
Arithmetic functions	
	() grouping
	^ exponentiation
	* multiplication
	/ division
	+ addition
	- subtraction
Fixed argument functions	
floor(n)	returns the maximum integer less than or equal to n
ceil(n)	returns the minimum integer greater than or equal to n
abs(n)	returns the absolute value of n
mod(m, n)	returns m modulus n
sin(n)	returns the sine of n (degrees)
cos(n)	returns the cosine of n (degrees)
ln(n)	returns the natural logarithm of n
log(m, n)	returns the logarithm of m with base n
exp(n)	returns e^n
round(m, n)	returns m rounded to n places
Variable argument functions	
min(a, b, \dots, n)	returns the minimum of values a, b, \dots, n
max(a, b, \dots, n)	returns the maximum of values a, b, \dots, n
mean(a, b, \dots, n)	returns the mean of values a, b, \dots, n
Random number generation functions	
unifrand(m, n)	returns a number from a uniform distribution between m and n
gaussrand(m, n)	returns a number from a Gaussian distribution with mean m and standard deviation n
prob(m)	generates a uniformly random number on the range [0, 1] and returns 1 (True) if this number is less than or equal to m ; else returns 0 (False)
SODAsim functions	
Legend	
shape	<p>specifies the index of a shape (numbering begins with shape 0) in one of the following ways:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * self : the reference shape * k : shape with index k * Nk : the kth neighbor of the reference shape (numbering begins at 1)
def = n	optional argument that will cause the function to return a default value of n if shape does not exist or if no shapes meet the given conditions ; default is 0 when not specified
conditions	<p>optional argument that specifies the set of shapes under consideration using:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> * keyword idx: refers to the index of the shape under consideration in n and t functions * keyword nid: refers to the neighbor index of the neighbor under consideration in n functions (e.g. a hexagon with six neighbors has neighbor indices 1, 2, 3, 4, 5, 6) * use parentheses to group * logical symbols: & (and), (or); & has priority over * comparator symbols: =, !=, <, >, <=, >= <p>Note: within conditions, state names evaluate to 1 if the shape under consideration is in that state (0 otherwise), and property names evaluate to the value of the property of the shape under consideration (e.g. ncount(S & P < 2) specifies the neighbors in state S with property P less than 2).</p>

Functions	
<code>not(k, def = n)</code>	returns 1 if $k = 0$, returns 0 if $k = 1$, and returns n if k is not 0 or 1
<code>xpos(shape, def = n)</code>	returns the x coordinate of the center point of <code>shape</code>
<code>ypos(shape, def = n)</code>	returns the y coordinate of the center point of <code>shape</code>
<code>exists(shape)</code>	returns 1 if <code>shape</code> exists; else returns 0
<code>instate(shape, S, def = n)</code>	returns 1 if <code>shape</code> is in state <code>S</code> ; else returns 0 Second argument may be 'S1 S2 ... Sn' if shape may be in any of multiple states
<code>ncount(conditions)</code>	returns the number of neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code> ; <code>ncount()</code> returns the number of neighbors of <code>shape</code>
<code>tcount(conditions)</code>	returns the number of total shapes that meet <code>conditions</code> ; <code>tcount()</code> returns the total number of shapes (same as keyword 'numshapes')
<code>val(shape, P, def = n)</code>	returns the value of property <code>P</code> of <code>shape</code>
<code>nrand(conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the index of a random neighboring shape that meets <code>conditions</code>
<code>trand(conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the index of a random <code>shape</code> that meets <code>conditions</code>
<code>nsamp(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the index of a shape proportionally sampled based on non-negative values of property <code>P</code> from set of neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code> (if all such values are 0, returns random shape from set)
<code>tsamp(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the index of a shape proportionally sampled based on non-negative values of property <code>P</code> from set of all shapes that meet <code>conditions</code> (if all such values are 0, returns random shape from set)
<code>nmin(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the minimum value of property <code>P</code> of the neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>tmin(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the minimum value of property <code>P</code> of the shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>nmax(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the maximum value of property <code>P</code> of the neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>tmax(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the maximum value of property <code>P</code> of the shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>nmean(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the mean value of property <code>P</code> of the neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>tmean(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the mean value of property <code>P</code> of the shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>nsum(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the sum of the values of property <code>P</code> of the neighboring shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>
<code>tsum(P, conditions, def = n)</code>	returns the sum of the values of property <code>P</code> of the shapes that meet <code>conditions</code>

Within expressions, the order of execution is as follows:

- 1) keywords: replacement of each SODAsim keyword with its value
- 2) Nk forms: replacement of Nk forms, where k is the neighbor index of a shape as shown on the NEIGHBORS page, with the index of that neighbor; if the k th neighbor does not exist and no default value is given as a function argument, Nk is replaced with 0
- 3) arithmetic expressions: evaluated in order $()$, \wedge , $*$ and $/$, $+$ and $-$ (PEMDAS)
 - arithmetic and SODAsim functions use parentheses to hold arguments, so are evaluated with same priority as $()$.
 - When n/t functions are evaluated:
 - state name `S` is replaced with 1 (True) if the shape under consideration is in state `S`, otherwise replaced with 0 (False)
 - property name `P` is replaced with the value of property `P` of the shape under consideration
 - The names of states and properties should appear only within functions.
 - expressions are evaluated from innermost to outermost parentheses
- 4) comparators ($\&$ is evaluated before $|$)
 - $a \& b$ (a and b): returns 1 if a and b are both equal to 1
 - $a | b$ (a or b): returns 1 if a or b or both are equal to 1
- 5) logical operators ($=$, \neq , $<$, $>$, \leq , \geq): each logical operator must have a number to the left and right

- logical operators may be chained together in constructs such as “ $a < b \leq c$ ”, where the expression will return 1 if $a < b$ and $b \leq c$ (all logical operators must return True) and otherwise return 0

Transition conditions from state S to other states are evaluated in the order in which they are listed. Click on the “Edit” option below the state name on the state diagram to display this list, and use the \uparrow and \downarrow arrow buttons to adjust the order of transitions. If a transition condition evaluates to 1, then the transition will occur, and no other transition conditions will be evaluated. “True” can be used as a transition expression if the transition must always occur when given the opportunity. If no transition conditions are met, a shape will remain in its current state. A “self transition” from state S to state S may be added, in which case transition property values will be calculated.

If there is a probability $P_{A \rightarrow B}$ of a transition from state A to state B occurring within t time steps, the probability $p_{A \rightarrow B}$ of this transition occurring within a single time step is $1 - \exp\left(\frac{\ln(1 - P_{A \rightarrow B})}{t}\right)$.

The list of arguments in SODAsim functions always follows the general order: shape index or property, conditions, default value.

INITIAL STATES

Time step 0 is the beginning of a simulation. The data of time step 1 is calculated based on the data of time step 0, and the data of time step 2 from the data of time step 1, and so forth. On this page, the user assigns each shape at time step 0 to a state, allowing any property values to be computed for shapes at time step 0. To assign states, first select a state from the drop-down menu, then either click on shapes directly or click on one of the five selectors below the drop-down menu. Shapes may be removed from a state by clicking on them, and all shapes in a state may be removed from that state using the “No shapes” selector. To assign a randomly selected number of shapes, select the desired state from the drop-down menu, then enter the number of shapes next to the “Randomly chosen shapes” selector, then click the selector; only unassigned shapes will be assigned. All shapes can be unassigned by using the “Clear initial states” button.

A parameters file may be saved by clicking the “Save parameters” button, which triggers a popup, and entering a file name (.txt extension will be added automatically) and clicking the “Save button”. Saved parameters files will be saved to the directory containing SODAsim unless a file path is included in the file name.

SIMULATION

- **New simulation** (button): erases all simulation data to begin a new simulation
- **Compute steps** (button): opens a submenu allowing the user to compute and append time steps to the simulation
- **View simulation** (button): requires that at least one step has been computed

- **View simulation summary** (button): opens a popup containing a graph for selected content with adjustable axes and gridlines; points on graph may be clicked to display more information
- **Seconds per step** (entry): accepts a float value indicating the minimum length of time to display each time step (computer lag may cause time steps to display for longer than this value)
- **Select view** (drop-down menu): presents options of which data to view
 - “states”: displays the corresponding color of the state of each shape during each time step
 - <property name>: displays the value of the selected property of each shape during each time step by mapping this value to the selected color scheme; if a property name is selected, the following fields appear:
 - **Select color scheme** (drop-down menu): presents options for color-coding property values
 - **Value range** (*optional* entries): the minimum and maximum values corresponding to the ends of the color scheme; values lower than the minimum appear white, and values higher than the maximum appear black. Setting these entries prevents outlier values from dominating the range of the color scheme. If one of these entries is left blank, it will automatically be assigned as the minimum or maximum property value present within the computed time steps. Note that if more time steps are computed and value range entries are not set for property value displays, the color-coding may be readjusted to account for greater range in the minimum and maximum values displayed.
- **Compile simulation data** (button): compiles data used for display once viewing parameters have been entered and displays time step indicator and shape information canvas. The “Play” and “Pause” buttons display the simulation like a video. To skip to a particular time step, the triangular indicator may be clicked and dragged, or the desired time step may be entered in time step entry box below the indicator.
- **Save steps** (button): opens a popup allowing the user to save the simulation that may be later loaded using the “Load steps” button
- **Load steps** (button): opens a popup allowing the user to load a simulation (parameters must be identical as those used to generate the loaded simulation) that was previously saved using the “Save steps” button; steps may be appended to the end of a loaded simulation using the “Compute steps” button
- **Spreadsheet** (button): opens a popup allowing the user to create a spreadsheet (xlsx format) containing all states and properties data for all shapes during all time steps

Quality control

On each page of SODAsim, inputs and processes are checked for completion before the user may progress to the next page. If requirements have not been met, an error message will display and direct the user to the missed or incorrect input so that it may be remediated. In many cases, the error message will describe the problem.

Each keyword and function has been tested to verify that it is interpreted and evaluated correctly by the program. Expressions are evaluated inside a try-except structure, so incorrectly written expressions will not cause the program to crash, and will instead produce an error message directing the user to the expression.

To check the basic functioning of the program, verify that an example simulation can be loaded and run without an error message displaying. To do this, double-click on the SODAsim icon to launch the program and select the “Example simulation” option on the main GUI window. On the popup window that appears, choose any example simulation from the “Choose an example simulation” dropdown menu and click the “Load” button. After a brief pause, the message “Loading complete! You may exit this popup.” should appear. Close the popup window and on the main window, click the “Next” button five times, then the “Propagate” button (wait for shapes to complete propagation), then the “Next” button three more times. Click the “Compute steps” button, enter “10” (without the quotation marks) into the “Additional steps to add” text entry field, and click the “Compute” button. Once this process has completed and the “Viewing parameters” options appear, enter “1” (without the quotation marks) into the “Seconds per step” text entry field, select “states” under the “Select view” dropdown menu, and click the “Compile simulation data” button. Press the “Play” button once it appears and verify that the simulation reaches step 10. If this process can be completed, then the software is working.

For a custom simulation instead of a preloaded example, an error message with a brief explanation will display within the GUI if the user has failed to supply necessary information or has supplied information that is incompatible with the program. If this happens, the user can correct the problematic input and continue.

(2) Availability

Operating system

SODAsim is programmed in Python 3.11.5, which is compatible with Windows 8+

Programming language

SODAsim is programmed in Python 3.11.5, which is compatible with Windows 8+ and built into an executable with PyInstaller 6.19.0.

Additional system requirements

The executable is less than 43 MB and memory requirement for usage scales with the number of shapes within the array of shapes, number of properties added to the state diagram, and time steps computed. A computer screen must be able to support the size of the GUI, which is 1000 pixels (width) by 700 pixels (height).

Dependencies

As a standalone executable built with PyInstaller, SODAsim does not require installation of any other software.

List of contributors

Same as authors.

Software location:

Archive

Name: Zenodo

Persistent identifier: 10.5281/zenodo.21142387

Licence: Open license under which the software is licensed

Publisher: Morgan Young

Version published: 1

Date published: 02/07/26

Code repository

Name: GitHub

Identifier: 1265312802

Licence: GPL-3.0

Date published: 10/06/26

Language

Python 3.11.5

(3) Reuse potential

SODAsim can be used to model any state diagram consisting of states and scalar values operating on a regularly spaced and connected array of shapes. Users define the states, state transitions, and properties, so the program can be applied to models in any field that fit into this setup. Examples built into SODAsim include contagious illness spread (with variations that involve disease mutation, vaccination schedules, and unequal contagious potential of neighbors), simple diffusion and thermodynamic systems, and pathfinding. The flexible integration of spatial architecture, state dynamics, and scalar property modeling makes SODAsim particularly adaptable for biological systems involving emergent multicellular or polymicrobial behavior. For example, potential biological applications include

modeling host–microbiome interactions, tissue barrier dynamics, developmental patterning, and emergent behaviors arising from polymicrobial communities.

SODAsim is a standalone software built with PyInstaller, so no additional dependencies or support are required. If desired, users may add to the native functions of the code under the “simplify” function, following the style in which the others are programmed.

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Competing interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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